

Vanadium. Part X, Quinoline-, Isoquinoline- and Pyrazine Carboxylic Acid Complexes of Oxovanadium (IV)

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Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid (8-QH) reacts with vanadium (IV) to produce light yellow $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(8\text{-Q})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and six coordinated $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(8\text{-Q})_2]$ (where X=Pyridine aniline, α -picoline etc). Both the series give usual one unpaired electron magnetic moment. Isoquinoline carboxylic acid furnishes the light cream coloured mother compound but apparently no amine or base adduct. Pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (PyrH_2) produces $[\text{VO}(\text{Pyr})](\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ and with pyridine $[\text{VO}(\text{Py})(\text{Pyr})]$, in which the ligand behaves as a bidentate with the complexes being polymeric. These are also all paramagnetic. The electronic spectra reveals three distinct bands which is in keeping with the spectral characteristics observed in similar other systems.

This study is a part of a comprehensive programme on oxovanadium (IV) complexes of pyridino-, quinoline- and pyrazine carboxylic acid ligands. In two earlier papers^{1,2} of this series lengthy reports have appeared on the vanadium (IV) complexes of quinoline-2-carboxylic acids and a number of mono-, di- and tri-carboxylic acids of the heterocyclic pyridine. In quinoline-2-carboxylic acid the metal was a part of a five membered ring system and we thought it worthwhile to look into other parallel systems with five or six numbered rings so that a comparative study with regard to the syntheses and properties of the resulting oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes may be made. It was with this end in view that we studied the interaction of oxo-vanadium (IV) with the following three ligands.

Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid (8-QH)

Isoquinoline-2-carboxylic acid (IsoQH)

Pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (Pyr H_2)

Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid (8-QH) reacts with oxo-vanadium (IV) sulphate around pH 4-4.5 to furnish a crystalline, light yellow complex, which has been characterised as $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(8\text{-Q})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. The complex loses one H_2O rather easily and the second with decomposition of the complex zone, thus leading us to formulate this as a monohydrate.* Repeated reflux with methanol gave indications of a pale green substance, in a rather doubtful purity. These observations are reminiscent of what was observed several years ago with respect to the quinoline-2-carboxylic acid. The yellow sample is para-

1. Dutta & Lahiri, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, in press.
2. Dutta & Ghosh, in press.

*Thermogravimetric and differential thermal analytical evidences will be presented shortly.

magnetic (1.78 B.M.). The infra red spectra definitely indicates a strong vanadyl band around 965 cm^{-1} and definite infra red bands at 885 cm^{-1} and 767 cm^{-1} give evidence with regard to a coordinated aqua molecule. Thus the complex may apparently be viewed as a six coordinated monomer but its extreme insolubility in all organic solvents may also be taken as an indication of some polymeric character. Just as we did for the quinoline-2-carboxylic acid, here too we investigated the action of a number of potential monodentate donors, such as pyridine, α -picoline, aniline, dimethyl aniline, benzidine, tetrahydrofuran and dioxan. Such adduct formation has been studied in particular with the ligands, acetylacetone, quinaldinic acid and 5-nitroquinaldinic acid. These studies and the results thereof may expose the extent to which these adducts are stable and their formation may be related to the basic character of the ligands. The above donors produced complexes of the usual type $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(\text{8-Q})_2]$ of dark olive-green colour (pyridine/aniline type) to ash green for the dioxan, tetrahydrofuran type. However, in general, these adducts appeared to be less stable than their quinoline 2-carboxylic acid analogues. On storage in a desiccator over months, the samples slowly assumed a dull colour with the smell of the amines being detectable. Since complexes are all donor-acceptor system and since it is reasonable to assume that the electron acceptor property of a metal ion in a particular oxidation state is a certain quantity, we believe quinoline-8-carboxylic acid forms a stronger donor compared to quinoline-2-carboxylic acid, in so far as the complexes $[\text{VOQ}]_2$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{8-Q})_2]$ are concerned. An interesting series of articles have appeared with regard to copper (II) where adduct formation of a four coordinated copper (II) complex leading to a five coordinated species has been shown to fall off with the increasing formation constant of the four coordinated species. We have made a detailed thermal dissociation studies of a series of comparable oxovanadium (IV) complexes of these two quinoline carboxylic acids and we will examine these results critically in a forthcoming paper. The magnetic susceptibility of all these complexes are normal ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=1.78-1.9\text{ BM}$)

TABLE I
Magnetic Measurements

Complex	Dis ⁴ Corr. $\times 10^6$	$\lambda_m(\text{Corr}) \times 10^6$	$\mu_{\text{eff}}(\text{B.M.})^*$
Bis-Quinoline-8-carboxylato oxo-Vanadium IV dihydrate. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	204.28	1290.28	1.78
Pyridine-bis-quinoline-8 carboxylato oxo-Vanadium IV $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$	230.62	1411.6	1.86
α -Picoline-bis quinoline-8 carboxylato-oxo-Vanadium IV $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$	241.40	1264.4	1.76
Aniline-bis-quinoline-8 carboxylato-oxo-Vanadium IV $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$	242.34	1309.3	1.79
Dimethylaniline-bis-quinoline-8 carboxylato-oxo-Vanadium IV $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N})]$	249.26	1241.96	1.75
Tetrahydrofuran-bis quinoline-8-Carboxylato oxo-Vanadium IV $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O})]$	226.0	1538	1.94
Benzidine-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-oxo-Vanadium IV $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2)]$	299.9	1520	1.93
Pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylato oxo-Vanadium IV tetrahydrate $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	115.0	1335	1.81

* μ_{eff} was calculated from the relation $\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.84 \sqrt{\lambda(\text{corr.}) \times \text{T. B.M.}}$ where T=absolute temperature.

The complexes also exhibit the vanadyl band around 965 cm^{-1} . The coordinated amines or the oxygen donors are lost on heating giving the yellow brown $[\text{VO}(\text{S-Q})_2]$ just as had been observed for the quinoline-2-carboxylic acid complexes. Besides, a vanadium (V) complex, oxo-hydroxo-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-vanadium (V) has also been isolated. This is yellow and diamagnetic.

With isoquinoline carboxylic acid we succeeded in obtaining the mother compound in the form of pale cream coloured crystalline powder. The complex had no water, and the composition apparently is $[\text{VO}(\text{iso-Q})_2]$. Repeated attempts to obtain adducts with heterocyclic bases or other oxygen donors failed. The above complex is as usual paramagnetic.

Pyrazine carboxylic acid was chosen because there was the possibility of two alternate structures, (1) the complex may behave as a bidentate and may still retain one N and COOH unused and uncoordinated; (2) it may function as a bidentate at the same time using the other N and COOH for further complexation giving rise to a polymeric structure. The possibility of functioning as a quadridentate is extremely poor as it would mean great strain. We have isolated a complex which gives vanadium: ligand ratio as 1:1 and analysed as $[\text{VO}(\text{Pyr})] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. This supports a polymeric structure.

Since none of the complexes reported in this study was found suitable for spectral study, we have obtained the diffuse reflectance spectra of the olive green, $[\text{VO}(\text{Py})(\text{S-Q})]$. The spectra reveals three distinct peaks at $740\text{ m}\mu$ (13500 cm^{-1}), $560\text{ m}\mu$ (17800 cm^{-1}) and at $400\text{ m}\mu$ (25000 cm^{-1}). (Fig. 1). This is in keeping with the spectral characteristics observed in similar other systems and conforms to Ballhausen and Gray's model of Vanadyl Complexes, representing the electronic transitions from (1) dxy to dyz and dxz orbitals, (2) to dx^2-y^2 orbital and (3) finally to the dz^2 orbital.

FIG. 1

3. Dutta, Ghosh & Wendlandt, in press

4. Selwood. *Magnetochemistry*. Interscience, New York, p. 76, 1956.

5. Ballhausen and Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 111.

EXPERIMENTAL

Complexes of Quinoline 8-Carboxylic Acid (8QH). Quinoline-8-Carboxylic acid was prepared following standard procedure⁶.

Aquo-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV) Monohydrate.—Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid (0.4 g) was dissolved in hot water (25-30 ml) and gradually added to a solution of vanadyl sulphate pentahydrate (0.25 g) in hot water (2-3 ml). The pH of the resultant clear green solution was then raised to 4-4.5, with dilute ammonium hydroxide when a voluminous pale yellow precipitate was thrown down. It was digested on water bath for 15-20 min. filtered, washed with water followed by alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 11.31; N, 6.44; H_2O (loss at 115°-120°) 8.3. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$: V, 11.41; N, 6.3; H_2O , 8.5.

Pyridine-bis-quinoline-8-Carboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid (0.5 g) was dissolved in a mixture of absolute alcohol (20 ml) and pyridine (10 ml) and was then added to a solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g) in hot water (5 ml) when a clear brown solution was obtained. This was then left overnight at room temperature. Olive-green silky crystals were obtained, filtered, washed with alcohol till free from pyridine and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 10.33; N, 8.49. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$: V, 10.4, N, 8.57%.

The compound liberated pyridine on heating with caustic soda solution.

Aniline-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—The aniline compound was obtained as above replacing pyridine by aniline. This compound was also an olive green crystalline substance of a darker shade. Found: V, 9.98; N, 8.42. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$: V, 10.11; N, 8.33%.

This compound liberated aniline on heating with sodium hydroxide solution.

α -Picoline-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—Quinoline 8-carboxylic acid (0.4 g) was dissolved in a hot mixture of absolute alcohol (25 ml) and α -picoline (10 ml.) in a conical flask and added gradually with stirring to a solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g) in hot water (2-3 ml) when a yellowish green granular precipitate settled down. The conical flask was then heated on waterbath for 10 min. corked up and kept at room temperature for two days during which the precipitate changed colour to dirty green. It was then filtered, washed with alcohol till free from α -picoline smell and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V 10.03; N, 8.48. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})]$: V, 10.11, N, 8.33%.

Dimethylaniline-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—The same procedure as in the case of the above α -picoline compound was adopted here. The dried compound is a granular solid of dirty green colour. Found: V, 9.67; N, 7.96. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_{11}\text{N})]$: V, 9.58; N, 7.89%.

Benzidine-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—Freshly prepared yellow oxo-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-vanadium (IV) (0.5 g) was refluxed for 12-14 hr. with a solution of benzidine (1.0 g) in absolute alcohol (25 ml) when a deep dirty green crystalline product was obtained. It was filtered, washed repeatedly with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 8.50; N, 9.34. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2)]$: V, 8.57; N, 9.41%.

6. Campbell et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1845.

Tetrahydrofuran-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—Quinoline-8-carboxylic acid (0.4 g) was dissolved by heating in a mixture of absolute alcohol (25 ml) and tetrahydrofuran (10 ml) and is then gradually added to a solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g) in hot water (2-3 ml) when a yellowish green granular precipitate settled down. It was then warmed on water bath with more tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) for 5-6 min. and allowed to stand at room temperature for 5-6 hr. It was then filtered, washed repeatedly with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . The dried product was a pale green granular solid turning gummy on exposure to moist air. Found: V, 10.65; N, 5.91, loss at 160° , 15.07. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O})]$: V, 10.55; N 5.82, loss 14.9%.

Dioxan-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—This compound was obtained as above using dioxan in place of tetrahydrofuran and have similar characteristics. Found: V, 10.30; N, 5.70; loss at 135° , 18.0. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2)]$ V, 10.17; N, 5.61; loss, 17.7%.

Hydroxo-bis-quinoline-8-carboxylato-oxo-vanadium (V).—Solutions of ammonium vanadate (0.17 g) in hot water (10 ml) and quinoline 8-carboxylic acid (0.4g) in hot water (20 ml) were mixed and the pH of the solution adjusted to 2.5-3 by the addition of 2N H_2SO_4 when a yellow granular precipitate was thrown down. It was filtered, washed with water followed by alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . The dry product is a lemon yellow powder. (Found: V, 12.04; N, 6.45. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_2)_2]$: V, 11.91; N, 6.54%.

Complexes of Pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylic Acid.—Pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylic acid was prepared following standard method⁷.

Pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV) tetrahydrate.—Vanadyl sulphate pentahydrate (1.0 g) was dissolved in water and converted into vanadyl hydroxide by the action of sodium hydroxide and washed free from alkali and sodium sulphate. Pyrazine carboxylic acid (1.25 g) was then dissolved in hot rectified spirit (50 ml) and the vanadyl hydroxide was added to it and vigorously triturated in a mortar-pestle when a bright green solution with some green precipitate was obtained. It was then filtered and the filtrate cooled in ice when a crystalline leaf green compound was obtained. It was filtered, washed repeatedly with spirit and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 16.79; N, 9.09; H_2O (loss at $130-135^\circ$), 23.94. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$: V, 16.72; N, 9.18; H_2O , 23.6%.

Pyridine-pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—Freshly prepared above green compound (about 0.5 g) was heated on a steam bath with pyridine (5 ml) when a clear green solution was obtained which was evaporated to dryness. The residue was scratched with absolute alcohol and again evaporated to dryness. This process was repeated several times and finally it was filtered, washed with alcohol till free from pyridine smell, and dried over CaCl_2 . It is a brownish green crystalline solid. Found: V, 16.39; N, 13.55. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]$: V, 16.48; N, 13.46%.

A Complex of Isoquinaldinic Acid. Iso-quinadinic acid was prepared from isoquinoline (B.D.H.) following standard procedure⁸.

Bis-isoquinaldinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—Isoquinaldinic acid (0.4 g) was dissolved

7. R. G. Jones and K. C. McLaughlin, *Organic Synthesis*, Vol. 30 p. 86.

8. Padbery and Lulldwall., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1268.

in hot water (50 ml) and gradually added to a solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g) in hot water (5 ml) when a buff coloured granular precipitate was thrown down which on digestion on steam bath for 15 min. changed to cream colour. It was then filtered, washed with hot water followed by alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 12.50; N, 6.89. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2]$: V, 12.41; N, 6.81%.

General Experimental Procedures.—Vanadium was estimated as V_2O_5 after igniting the complexes to constant weight.

Nitrogen was determined by the semimicro-combustion technique.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined in a Gouy Balance using copper sulphate pentahydrate (E. Merck) as the calibrant.

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